

PACIFICUS

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“THE TEACHER OF DREAMS”

In class, she is stern but affectionate.
Teaching young minds to aspire and be patient
Business lessons, bold and bright,
She feels them into a future that is right.

She talks in numbers, in sales and trade,
Of those which risk, of plans well made.
A therapist with patience deep, wisdom wide,
She accompanies every step by their side

From balance sheets to profits earned,
This is how skills and formulas are learned.
She sows the seeds for enterprise,
And paths that let them rise and thrive.

Every case, every real-world test,
She also brings out all the best
In books, and in life,
She teaches with full of wisdom and bright

More than words can tell, she teaches.
She teaches them that failure is just another way
They learn, improve and find their stay.
That business isn't merely for profit to gain
But built on trust not greed nor vain.

With courage big she fuels the dream,
To chart their course, to show they fit in.
By ethics, skills, and vision grand
she shapes the future with her hand

These students, one day, are bold and free.
Will start their own economy.
And if they gleam, they'll remember me
The teacher who'd taught them all the way

While years lose their luster and time takes a high,
Her lessons are still alive — they are never died.
For knowledge offered heart and soul,
And will always be a lasting role

